

Electrochemical and Permeation Studies on Dowex-50 Supported Chloroplast Liquid Membranes

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Membrane potential and membrane conductance studies using Dowex-50 membrane, and sodium chloride and magnesium chloride solutions have been carried out to study the effect of supported chloroplast liquid membrane on its electrochemical characteristics. Permeation characteristics of the membrane system under comparable experimental conditions have also been investigated.

Liquid membrane generation using constituents of biomembranes has been demonstrated^{1,2}. Their suitability as model membrane systems has also been explored³. Light-induced electrical potential difference across liquid membrane bilayers generated from chloroplast extract have been studied by Srivastava *et al.*⁴. We have investigated permeation, membrane potentials and membrane conductance behaviour of Dowex-50 Kynar supported chloroplast liquid membrane using sodium chloride and magnesium chloride solutions of different concentration so as to examine the effect of the liquid membrane on electrochemical characteristics of the supporting ion exchange matrix. Pressure and potential driven permeation studies under comparable conditions have also been carried out.

Results and Discussion

Membrane potential data obtained using Dowex-50 membrane and sodium chloride and magnesium chloride solutions of different concentrations, with and without chloroplast extract, are given in Table 1. For liquid membrane formation, chloroplast extract (1 ml) was added to electrolyte solution (99 ml) kept on either side of the membrane. Volume of chloroplast extract needed for liquid membrane formation was ascertained on the basis of surface tension measurements. Difference in concentration in all these measurements was kept

fixed at 0.06 M. Under comparable conditions, sodium chloride yields higher potential. In both the cases membrane potential decreases with increase in concentration. The ion exchange membrane deswells with increase in concentration⁵, as a result of which membrane void volume increases. This leads to reduction in ion selectivity of the membrane and lowering of membrane potential. Presence of chloroplast also leads to lowering of the membrane potential in both the cases. This occurs because of formation of liquid membrane at the membrane-solution interface. The accumulation of surface active species in the membrane solution interphasial region also adversely affects membrane selectivity thereby resulting in decrease in membrane potential. Permeability data (Table 2) also support the above inference. The $(J_v/\Delta p)_{\Delta\phi=0}$ values were obtained from the slopes of $(J_v)_{\Delta\phi=0}$ versus Δp plots (Fig. 1). An increase in membrane permeability with increase in concentration arises on account of deswelling of the membrane matrix and consequent increase in membrane void volume. Equivalent membrane pore radius values obtained using the relationship⁶,

$$\gamma = \sqrt{8 \eta (J_v/\Delta P)_{\Delta P=0} / (A/1)} \quad (1)$$

are summarised in Table 3 alongwith membrane conductance and specific conductance of the experimental solutions. η represents coefficient of viscosity of the permeant.

Fig. 1. Variation of $(J_v)_{\Delta\phi=0}$ with pressure difference ΔP : (i) for 0.05 M sodium chloride and (ii) for 0.05 M magnesium chloride : (O) without chloroplast, (●) with chloroplast.

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE POTENTIAL VALUES (mV) AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS WITH DOWEX-50 MEMBRANE

$\Delta C = 0.06 M$

Concn M	NaCl		MgCl ₂	
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
0.04	33.67	28.22	15.30	12.52
0.06	20.79	18.14	12.43	10.10
0.08	14.35	13.03	9.68	7.48
0.10	12.64	11.09	6.53	4.64
0.12	9.81	8.73	5.04	2.80

(A) = without chloroplast extract. (B) = with chloroplast extract.

TABLE 2—HYDRODYNAMIC PERMEABILITIES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Concn. M	[($J_v/\Delta p$) $_{\Delta\phi=0}$] NaCl		[($J_v/\Delta p$) $_{\Delta\phi=0}$] MgCl ₂	
	$cm^5 s^{-1} dyne^{-1}$		$cm^5 s^{-1} dyne^{-1}$	
	(A) × 10 ⁻⁹	(B) × 10 ⁻⁹	(A) × 10 ⁻⁹	(B) × 10 ⁻⁹
0.04	4.0	3.4	8.8	7.5
0.05	10.4	8.7	10.0	8.9
0.06	18.6	16.7	11.3	9.6
0.08	50.0	26.7	13.8	12.0
0.10	56.0	40.0	44.4	37.0
0.12	58.0	50.0	48.0	45.0

(A) = without chloroplast extract. (B) = with chloroplast extract.

A/l is called membrane constant and is given by

$$A/l = \left(\frac{l}{\Delta\phi}\right)_{\Delta P=0} / K \quad (2)$$

where $(l/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta P=0}$ is membrane conductance and k the specific conductance of the permeating solution. Membrane conductance values were obtained from current voltage data (Figs. 2 and 3). The

equivalent pore radius is seen to increase with increase in concentration and it decreases in the presence of chloroplast extract.

Ion exchange membranes allow ionic migration with unequal ease and are accordingly endowed with permselectivity. Membrane permselectivity, in the case of a cation exchange membrane may be expressed as⁷

$$P_s = \frac{\bar{t}_+ - t_+}{1 - t_+} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{t}_+ is transport number of the cation in the membrane phase, t_+ denotes its transport number in solution. \bar{t}_+ values (Table 4) were estimated from membrane potential data using the relationships⁸,

$$(\Delta\phi)_{I=0} = (2\bar{t}_+ - 1) \frac{RT}{F} \ln c_2/c_1 \quad (4)$$

for sodium chloride. For magnesium chloride the corresponding relationship is

$$(\Delta\phi)_{I=0} = (3/2\bar{t}_+ - 1) \frac{RT}{F} \ln c_2/c_1 \quad (5)$$

Permselectivity values derived using equation (3) are presented in Table 4. Permselectivity is lowered in the presence of chloroplast liquid membrane in both the cases. It also decreases with increase in concentration consistent with progressive enhancement of membrane deswelling with concentration.

TABLE 3—MEMBRANE CONDUCTANCE DATA AND AVERAGE PORE RADIUS VALUES OF THE DOWEX-50 MEMBRANE

Concn M	$(I/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta\phi \rightarrow 0} \times 10^{-3}$ Ω^{-1}				$K \times 10^{-3}$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$		$r \times 10^5$ cm			
	NaCl		MgCl ₂		NaCl	MgCl ₂	NaCl		MgCl ₂	
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)			(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
0.04	2.6	1.8	1.1	1.0	5.54	1.716	2.5	0.8	3.1	3.0
0.05	3.0	2.0	1.6	1.3	5.57	2.496	3.7	4.2	3.3	3.4
0.06	3.6	2.9	1.8	1.4	5.60	2.803	4.6	4.8	3.5	3.7
0.08	4.8	3.7	2.0	1.6	5.65	3.120	6.5	5.4	3.9	4.1
0.10	5.5	4.5	2.6	2.2	5.68	4.056	6.4	6.0	7.0	7.0
0.12	6.3	5.6	3.0	2.5	5.71	4.680	6.1	6.0	7.3	7.8

(A) = without chloroplast (B) = with chloroplast

Fig 2 Dowex-50 membrane current-voltage behaviour for sodium chloride at different concentrations (A) without chloroplast and (B) with chloroplast (●) 0.04 (○), 0.05, (▲) 0.06, (Δ) 0.08, (■) 0.10, (□) 0.12 M

Ion exchange membrane used in the present investigation because of its pore size being of the order of 10^{-5} cm, may be treated as a macroporous membrane. The electrical double layer existing at the membrane solution interface may accordingly influence the permselectivity exhibited by the membrane. Some data on electroosmotic permeability obtained using 0.01 M sodium chloride

TABLE 4—TRANSPOR NUMBERS AND PERMSELECTIVITY VALUES

C M	NaCl			MgCl ₂			NaCl		MgCl ₂	
	\bar{t}_+	t_+	t_+	t_+	\bar{t}_+	t_+	P_s	P_s	P_s	P_s
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	
0.04	0.825	0.772	0.395	0.768	0.751	0.624	0.710	0.623	0.364	0.336
0.06	0.856	0.810	0.394	0.812	0.785	0.625	0.763	0.686	0.487	0.427
0.08	0.845	0.814	0.393	0.827	0.740	0.626	0.745	0.664	0.554	0.440
0.10	0.884	0.837	0.342	0.802	0.764	0.627	0.810	0.651	0.470	0.368
0.12	0.769	0.739	0.391	0.762	0.722	0.629	0.620	0.571	0.358	0.250

(A) = without chloroplast extract (B) = with chloroplast extract

Fig. 3 Dowex-50 membrane current-voltage behaviour for magnesium chloride at different concentrations : (A) without chloroplast and (B) with chloroplast : (●) 0.04, (○) 0.05, (▲) 0.06, (△) 0.08, (■) 0.10, (□) 0.12 M

Fig. 4 Variation of $(J_v)_{\Delta p=0}$ with potential difference, $\Delta\phi$: (i) for sodium chloride and (ii) for magnesium chloride: (○) without chloroplast, (●) with chloroplast at 0.01 M.

and magnesium chloride solutions with and without chloroplast extract are given in Fig. 4. The electroosmotic permeability values alongwith zeta potential values estimated using the relationship⁹,

$$\xi = \frac{4\pi \eta K (J_v/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta p=0}}{D (I/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta p=0}} \times 9 \times 10^4 \quad (6)$$

are given in Table 5. The $(J_v/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta p=0}$ is the electroosmotic permeation and D the dielectric constant of the permeant. A lowering of zeta potential in the presence of chloroplast liquid

membrane is observed in both the cases. Reduction in membrane permselectivity earlier observed may thus be attributed to lowering of the zeta potential.

TABLE 5—ELECTROOSMOTIC PERMEABILITIES AND ZETA POTENTIAL VALUES

Electrolyte	$(J_v/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta p=0}$ $\text{cm}^3 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$		ξ mV	
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
NaCl	3.0×10^{-5}	2.3×10^{-5}	39	37
MgCl ₂	4.3×10^{-5}	3.7×10^{-5}	8.5	8.6

(A) = without chloroplast extract. (B) = with chloroplast extract

Experimental

Membrane preparation was carried out as already reported². Dowex-50 (ion exchange capacity = $3.8 \text{ mequiv/dm}^{-3}$) (J. T. Baker Chemical Co., U.S.A.) was dispersed in a 20% solution of Kynar (Polyvinylidene fluoride) in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (Riedel-De Haevog-Seelze-Hannover) spread on clean, dried glass plate and kept in an electric oven at $80\text{--}90^\circ$. The membrane was then detached by immersion in distilled water. The water content of the 1 : 2 Kynar-Dowex membrane was determined in the usual manner¹⁰ and found to be 11.4%.

The membrane was fitted in an all-glass cell described elsewhere¹¹. It was transformed into Na^+ or Mg^{2+} forms by keeping it in 1 *M* sodium chloride or magnesium chloride solution. Thereafter the membrane was equilibrated with the desired experimental solution. The cross-sectional area of the membrane used was 1.56 cm^2 with thickness $2.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}$.

Chloroplast extraction was carried out using the reported procedure¹². Dried spinach leaves in a powder form were soaked in 80% acetone containing a pinch of calcium carbonate, and kept overnight. The solution was then filtered and the filtrate, chloroplast extract, was used as such for liquid membrane generation.

Membrane potential measurements with and without chloroplast were carried out as already reported¹³ using a HIL 2665 multimeter and saturated calomel electrodes. For the determination of membrane conductance, variation of current with potential, applied across the membrane, was studied. Salt-bridges positioned near the membrane faces were connected to saturated calomel electrodes for the application of potential difference. For current measurements, silver-silver chloride electrodes were used.

Hydrodynamic and electroosmotic permeabilities

were measured as already reported¹⁴ by recording movement of the liquid in a horizontally fixed capillary tube having a cross-sectional area of $12.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2$. Potential difference across the membrane was applied with the help of an indigenously made power supply using Ag/AgCl electrodes. All measurements were carried out at $35 \pm 0.5^\circ$ using an air thermostat.

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